

Economical, Ecological and Experience Values for Product-Service Systems

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Abstract: Product-Service System (PSS) Design is new trend in new product and service design. In this paper, the E3 concept composed of economical, ecological, and experience values is proposed so that the PSS concept design and evaluation can be conducted with E3 values viewpoints. Economical values include cost reduction and income enhancement which can be achieved by differentiation, market creation, customer acquisition and retention. Ecological values address the issues such as energy and water saving, dematerialization, reducing hazardous materials, reuse and recycling. Experience values deal with more people-oriented viewpoints including utilitarian and hedonic aspects. With the adoption of consumer value framework by Holbrook, extrinsic and intrinsic value dimension is used as the first classifier of experience value and other aspects of experience such as emotional, social, and epistemic are also considered. In conceptual design phase, E3 values can be used by mapping onto lifecycle steps to identify various stakeholders' requirements. Lifecycle steps and stages can be arranged with E3 value attributes in matrix form. By forced relationship analysis, stakeholders' requirements can be identified in systematic manner. During the evaluation phase, E3 values can be used to compare PSS concept with its alternatives. Based on the concept of E3 value, alternative solutions can be compared with each other and relative importance or perceived preference can be assessed during the concept evaluation phase. We demonstrate how E3 values are used during design phase with the PSS case of a meal assembly kitchen: how to incorporate E3 values in the divergent and convergent activities of PSS design is described.

Key words: *Product-Service System (PSS) Design, Economical Value, Ecological Value, Experience Value*

1. Introduction

As market competition is getting more intense and technological differentiation becomes difficult, the integration of products and services is recognized as the emerging paradigm in industry, and received attention in research. With the increased attention on user-centeredness, the integrated viewpoint of products and services rather than product-service dichotomy is emphasized. Whatever users want should be fulfilled with product or service elements together in the way of total solution or functional offering. Technological progress such as information and communication technology (ICT) and ecological recognition on sustainability accelerate the integration of products and services as well [1].

PSS (product-service system) is accepted as a new product strategy by leading firms in well developed countries in either way of service productization or product servitization. Examples of product and service integration can be found in various industries; parts of banking services were productized as an ATM (Automated Teller Machine), and manufacturers of music player or e-book reader provided music or e-book contents downloading service to their customers. PSS can be defined as a marketable set of products and services, jointly capable of fulfilling a user's need [2]. It was also defined as a system of products, services, supporting networks and infrastructure that is designed to satisfy customer needs and have a lower environmental impact than traditional business models [3]. Another definition of PSS can be found as an integrated body of products and services and communication strategies that was conceived, developed and promoted by a network of actors to generate values for society [4]. Various definitions of PSS by previous researchers have the notion in common that main goal of PSS is to create additional value by integrating products and services.

Value is considered as the complex and ambiguous concept in various research fields. The evolving service-centered logic for marketing puts an emphasis on value, especially the value perceived by the customer or market. According to Khalifa [5], value research efforts can be classified into component model, benefit/cost ratio model, and means-ends model and he emphasized that dynamics over time and complexity for each stakeholders should be considered. During the design process of products, services, or PSSs, value research can help in identifying customer wants and needs early in the ideation or fuzzy front end, identifying factors or attributes that influence customer judgments, determining the relative importance of value-related attributes, and determining how offerings are viewed on each of these attributes relative to the customer's alternatives [6].

In this paper, based on literature survey on previous value research and investigation of PSS cases, value classification for PSS design and implementation during PSS design are proposed. Then with the example of PSS design case how value framework can be applied in the design process of PSS is explained as well.

2. E3 Values for PSS Design

As many successful examples of product and services integration came out in market, PSS is being recognized as an alternative solution or new product strategy in market and research area as well. Goedkoop et al indicated economical and ecological factors as the main drivers of PSS design. In the report for Netherland government, they proposed E2 vector as an evaluation framework for PSS, which consist of ecological burden and economic potential as well [2]. In consistent with E2 vector, MEPSS introduced triple winning concept with three Ps, which are people, profit, and planet, as main benefits of introducing PSS [7]. MEPSS emphasized on decoupling value creation and environmental impact by balancing the dimensions of people, planet and profit. In the same context, authors of this paper would like to propose the E3 value classification for PSS design, which are composed of economic, ecological, and experience value. For the viewpoint of stakeholders, economic values tend to be more related with product or service providers, experience values are more related with product users or service receivers. In E3 concept, experience value for customer of PSS, which includes both of utilitarian and hedonic dimensions, is more emphasized.

2.1. Economical Value

Business factors are considered as main drivers of PSS. By adding service or product elements respectively, product-oriented or service-oriented companies can attain differentiation from their competitors, enhanced relationship with their customers, and creation of new market. Examples of economical value in PSS can be found in Korean market. Samsung differentiated their cell phone by providing anycalland.com services from their competitors. Woongjin Coway, one of Korean home appliance manufacturer, could attain more than one million subscribers during first five years by introducing rental and home-visiting maintenance services in water purifier market. SK telecom provided phone upgrade services for free in order for customer retention. With the revenue or profit pool concept, economic values can be transformed into monetary value in general and compared with each other quantitatively. In addition to the viewpoint of product manufacturer or service provider, economic value for various stakeholders can be found as well. For example, users might seek economic value such as mileage earning or more discounts from PSS consumption. Economic value for employee as a service provider also should be considered carefully for better service quality. In our value hierarchy, economic value contains income enhancement and cost reduction as can be seen in figure1.

2.2. Ecological Value

Ecological value is another main driver of PSS introduction. United Nation Environments Programme (www.unep.org) has been active in promoting sustainable consumption and production by introducing eco-design, green procurement, and product-service system as options of sustainable consumption patterns. Sustainability is now considered as must option for innovation. Several companies utilize compliances as opportunities and continue to change their value chain more sustainable [8]. By designing product and services more sustainable and developing new business model, ecological values such as energy and water saving, dematerialization, reduction of hazardous materials, and promotion of reuse or recycle can be attained.

2.3. Experience Value

Pine and Gilmore (1998) argued that experiences represent the step in the evolution of economy as products and services become more commoditized. Creating value in such an environment requires staging memorable experiences that unfold over time [9]. Experience can be characterized by dynamics in use environment, customer participation, and social interaction. And designing the experiences should be focused on how participation and interaction can be enhanced to create successful experience by designing activities, physical layout, and social interaction [10].

Customer perceived values aroused by the use of product or services can be classified into utilitarian value and hedonic value. Batra and Ahtola supported the presence of distinct utilitarian and hedonic components, which have been referred to as thinking and feeling dimensions [11]. Sheth et al regarded consumer choice as a function of multiple consumption value dimensions and that these dimensions make varying contributions in different choice situations. They suggested five dimensions including social, emotional, functional, epistemic and conditional value, relating specifically to the perceived utility of a choice [12]. Utilitarian values are more related basic functions and features of product or services. Traditional viewpoint of quality on product or services can be adopted in construction of utilitarian value. ISO software quality model includes functionality, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability as sub-attribute of internal and external quality [13]. SERVQUAL

model suggested by Zeithalm includes five dimensions of service quality, which are tangibles, reliabilities, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy [14]. Holbrook proposed consumer value framework to distinguish eight types of consumer value. According to his typology of consumer value, there are three dimensions of consumer value which are (1) extrinsic versus intrinsic, (2) self-oriented versus others-oriented, and (3) active versus reactive [15]. Extrinsic value pertains to a means-ends relationship whereas intrinsic value occurs when some consumption experience is appreciated as an end in itself. Fiore and Ogle also used similar distinction between experiential and utilitarian dimensions in describing shopping experience [16].

In this paper, experience values are classified into extrinsic and intrinsic at the first level. Extrinsic value is classified into functional and social value again. For the case of social value, in addition to the extrinsic social value such as status or esteem, intrinsic dimension such as religion and spirituality seems to be applicable in PSS design as well. Intrinsic value includes social, emotional and epistemic value. Emotional value can be classified into active and reactive emotional value with the adoption of Holbrook's framework. Value hierarchy can be expanded with sub-entities respectively. For example, by adoption of CES (consumption emotion set), reactive emotional value can be expanded to have sub-entities of positive emotions associated with consumption such as joy, excitement, contentment, surprise, and so on [17]. By the use of similar approaches, social value and epistemic values can be also expanded by adoption of previous value researches and PSS case studies. Social value in mobile service design can be found in the way that membership service of mobile operators in Korea incorporated homogeneous experience for their subscribers, and at the same time heterogeneous value can be realized from classified membership, for example VIP membership. In Korea, the ring back tone service made great success, which achieved the social value of considering others [18]. According to the recent special report on service design, people are becoming less interested in stuff alone – products or commodities – and far more interested in an all-embracing experience as they interact with a product or service [19].

Figure 1. E3 Values for PSS Design

3. Incorporating E3 Values in PSS Design

E3 values proposed in this paper can be used effectively during divergent and convergent thinking in PSS design. During the phase of user requirement analysis and idea generation, hierarchical set of value classification can be used as a reference for systematic brainstorming. For each lifecycle steps, E3 value attributes can be used as stimuli for creative ideation. During the concept evaluation stage, values perceived by each target customers can be evaluated and compared with competitive solutions including existing product or services. New concept of PSS can be reviewed whether it is well balanced in terms of E3 values and strategically aligned.

3.1. Divergent Thinking incorporating E3 Values

The design of PSS starts from identification of customer requirements and subsequent value proposition to effectively reflect customers' potential needs and wants. To extract customer requirements, activity modeling cycle (AMC) approach can be used [20]. Graphical representation model modified from AMC model can be used to investigate life-cycle steps, involved stakeholders and the value delivery chain in an integrated fashion, as shown in its general form in Figure 2 [21]. This approach facilitates an analysis of the considered product from which a new PSS is to be designed. The life-cycle steps of the product are divided into pre, during and post phases, which will be helpful in expanding consideration domain from traditional focus on pre-stage into during-stage and post-stage. The AMC implies the notion of a repetitive cycle of life-cycle steps; hence the circular form and the arrows indicate their sequence. For each step in the AMC, the primary stakeholder is firstly identified and then secondary and tertiary stakeholders are identified. The identified stakeholders are located near the specific steps as circular form. The primary stakeholders are located close to the step, and secondary and tertiary ones are then located outside. In AMC, the specific needs and wants are also addressed in each step node, as shown in Figure 2. These needs and wants will be linked later with values to be pursued in the subsequent design phases.

Figure 2. Life-cycle Stage Analysis (modified from AMC)

During the phase of requirement identification, E3 value framework can be used as a reference system by constructing the horizontal axis in relationship analysis matrix as shown in Table 1. Vertical axis can be filled with life-cycle steps in pre, during, and post stages derived from life-cycle stage analysis. By the use of forced relationship analysis between values and life-cycle steps, customer or user requirements can be derived in efficient and systematic manner. In addition to requirement identification for existing products or services, it will be helpful in ideation of non-existing or more innovative PSS design. When no supplier is currently able or willing to provide value, customers perceive that value as a potential attribute. Although these potential value attributes are not articulated by customers, they can be considered as the basis of innovation. Value attributes introduced in PSS would be perceived in market after all and evaluated in market. Another important issue in this approach is to consider personas. Scenarios are generated for each persona with consideration of various contextual variables, and then activities derived from each scenario are used in matrix analysis to relate with value attributes.

Table 1. Matrix Analysis between Life-cycle Steps and E3 Values

The diagram illustrates a 3D matrix for analyzing life-cycle steps against E3 values across three stakeholder levels. The vertical axis represents Life-Cycle Steps (Pre, During, Post) with sub-steps 1 through 9. The horizontal axis represents E3 Values, categorized into Economic, Ecological, Experience, and Intrinsic. The depth axis represents Stakeholder levels (1, 2, 3). The matrix cells contain specific value attributes and User Requirements (UR) codes. For example, in the 'Pre' stage, 'Income Enhancement' is linked to UR1, and 'Health' is linked to UR2. In the 'During' stage, 'Economic' values like 'Excitement' and 'Reliability' are linked to UR3, UR4, UR5, and UR6. 'Ecological' values like 'Recycling' and 'Health' are linked to UR7, UR8, UR9, and UR10. 'Experience' values like 'Fun' and 'Leisure' are linked to UR11, UR12, UR13, and UR14. 'Intrinsic' values like 'Active' and 'Emotional' are linked to UR15, UR16, UR17, and UR18. The 'Post' stage shows 'Income Enhancement' linked to UR19 and UR20, and 'Health' linked to UR21 and UR22. The matrix also includes 'User Requirements' (UR) codes for each stakeholder level, ranging from UR1 to UR29.

Proposed approach was tested and implemented during PSS design workshop in June, 2010 as shown in figure 3. With more than sixty attendants from industry and academia, hands-on workshop was successfully hosted by Creative Design Institute of Sunkyunkwan University. With colorful sticky papers and E3 value hierarchy printed on shareable white board, attendants can exercise the systematic ideation and classification along with economical, ecological, and experience value dimensions.

Figure 3. Divergent Thinking incorporating E3 Values (PSS Design Tutorial Workshop, 2010, Seoul, Korea)

3.2. Convergent Thinking incorporating E3 Values

In evaluating PSS concepts during the convergent phase, relative comparison of alternative solutions should be conducted from the perspectives of created values. When one considers new PSS concept which consists of various product and service elements, various set of competitive or alternative products and services in market could be found. These alternatives can be evaluated along with E3 value attributes respectively and the overall comparison can be made from proper aggregation of respective evaluations as depicted in Figure 4. By the use of E3 value framework during the evaluation of PSS concepts, overall competitiveness of considered PSS concepts can be compared with other alternative solutions in terms of customer perceived values.

Figure 4. E3 Value Evaluation of PSS Concepts

4. Case Example

Now we demonstrate how E3 values are used using the PSS case of meal assembly kitchen. The meal assembly kitchen can be thought as a PSS concept derived from an existing product, for example an oven. Meal assembly kitchen is an innovative business and service concept in meal preparation that eliminates menu planning, shopping, pre-work and clean-up by moving the meal assembly process out of people's kitchens into specially equipped spaces staffed with various service providers as shown in figure 5. Assuming the case that the meal assembly kitchen PSS is designed from an oven product, user requirements of an oven are generated from the life cycle of an oven. The entire life-cycle of an oven is divided into three phases such as pre, during and post phases, and associated life-cycle steps, stakeholders and issues are identified to be presented in a graphical way as shown in Figure 6. The pre phase is composed of design and manufacture, sale and purchase, and delivery and install. The during phase includes preparing ingredients, baking foods, and taking out foods from oven. After dining, the post phase including washing, cleaning oven, maintaining and disuse of oven follows. For each step, the stakeholders in the oven's life-cycle are identified. For example, in the first step of life cycle, oven design and manufacture step in pre stage, it can be seen that various stakeholders such as producer, designer, seller, installer, and potential users are inter-related each other. Their requirements and needs are identified by mapping onto E3 values framework as shown in Table 2. For example, producer of oven needs to identify potential users' needs on oven, and it can be mapped onto customer acquisition attribute of economic value.

Figure 5. Meal Assembly Kitchen (www.mealassembly.net)

Figure 6. Life-cycle Stage Analysis of a Product - Oven

Table 2. Matrix Analysis between Life-cycle Steps and E3 Values in Meal Assembly Kitchen PSS case

Life-Cycle Steps vs. E3 Values Matrix		Income Enhancement	Cost Reduction	Ecological Value			Experience Value											
							Extrinsic				Intrinsic							
				Functional				Social	Emotional		Social	Epistemic						
				Saving	Recycling	Health	Excellence		Efficiency	Reliability			Convenience	Active	Reactive			
Pre	Oven Design & Manufacture		Low Cost Easy Manufacturing															
	Oven Sale & Purchase	Provide Recipe	Low Cost				Oven Usage											
	Delivery & Install						Wide Space for Install	Quick Delivery	Safe & Reliable Delivery									
During	Prepare Ingredients	Ingredients Supply		Reduce transportation to market	Reduce Food Waste	Organic Foods	Cooking Methods for Various Ovens			Prepare Ingredients	Other's Recipe							Learn New Recipe
	Cook Foods	Expert Help and Cooking Class								Pre-Heating Expert Help	Social Reputation & Know-How	Time Killing						Expert Lesson
	Take Out Foods	Entering Fee (Party Place)					Wide Space for Dine Various Dishes	Time Saving	Safety		Food Contest		Stylish Food	Sharing Foods with Others				Recipe Exchange
Post	Wash Dishes						Wide Space for Washing	Washing Service	Safety			Dish Washing Game						
	Cleaning Oven					Regular Cleaning												Cleaning Know-How
	A/S & Maintenance		Low Cost Maintenance	Preventive Maintenance	Parts Sharing													Maintenance Training
	Disuse		Save Disposal Cost															

For evaluation of meal assembly kitchen, several alternative solutions for potential customers are selected, which are cases of *restaurant dinner*, *potluck party*, and *hosting dinner at home* respectively. Every alternatives considered during evaluation are composed of product and service elements respectively. For example, product elements such as oven, utensil, ingredients, and cookbook are involved in cooking and dining process. Basic service activities such preparing ingredients, making foods, setting up tables, having dinner, washing dishes are all used while their actors and roles are assigned differently. By use of AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process), four alternatives including meal assembly kitchen were evaluated along with the evaluation criteria composed of E3 values. Evaluation was carried out by twenty five undergraduate students in Sungkyunkwan University and commercial software (www.expertchoice.com) was used for rating and integration. The meal assembly kitchen

PSS is evaluated together with other alternatives in terms of economical, ecological, and experience values as shown in Figure 7. For example, the meal assembly kitchen was evaluated high in terms of economic value as differentiation or new market creation options for oven manufacturer, food suppliers, or place providers seem to be possible. From the viewpoint of ecological value, it will be helpful in reducing food waste and promoting recycling. By providing food ingredients and various recipe, convenience and effectiveness can be enhanced in terms of functional value. Spacious cooking and dining place could possibly enhance the active and reactive emotional value. Provision of new recipe and food styling might increase epistemic experience value for potential customers. In addition to those, facilitated social interaction in meal assembly kitchen was also evaluated higher than other alternatives in terms of hedonic social value.

Figure 7. Evaluation of PSS Concept of Meal Assembly Kitchen incorporating E3 Values

5. Summary and Future Research

In this paper, E3 value concept of economical, ecological, and experience values is proposed as a main driver of PSS design and how to incorporate E3 values in PSS design is explained. E3 value-sets proposed in this paper do not set in stone, and they are adaptable based on individual design cases. Both of top-down and bottom-up approaches should be continued to derive more rich and comprehensive E3 value sub-entities in various PSS design cases. In the top-down approach, a comprehensive value ontology and close association among stakeholders, activities, contexts, and value attributes need to be investigated. In the bottom-up approach, more cases of PSS will be designed or surveyed and then analyzed so that the E3 value hierarchy can be enriched for more flexible utilization in new PSS design.

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6. References

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